

ENHANCE SOIL HEALTH IN ALPINE AND ATLANTIC BIOGEOGRAPHICAL REGIONS

EU Mission 'A Soil Deal for Europe'

Life on Earth depends on healthy soils. Soils are not only the foundation of our food systems. They also provide clean water and habitats for biodiversity while contributing to climate resilience.

Between 60 and 70% of EU soils are unhealthy; one centimetre of soil can take hundreds of years to form but can be lost in just a single rainstorm or industrial incident.

The EC launched the Mission 'A Soil Deal for Europe'- Horizon Europe programme -to create 100 living labs and lighthouses in rural and urban areas to drive the transition to healthy soils by 2030.

THE MISSION WILL:

- > Create knowledge and solutions for soil health,
- > Advance the development of a harmonised framework for soil monitoring in Europe,
- > Increase people's awareness of the vital importance of soils,
- > Support the EU's ambition to lead on global commitments, notably the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and contribute to the European Green Deal targets.*

 [*more information in the Mission implementation plan.](#)

THE 8 MISSION OBJECTIVES

1 Reduce desertification	2 Conserve soil organic carbon stocks	3 Stop soil sealing & increase re-use of urban soils	4 Reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration
5 Prevent erosion	6 Improve soil structure to enhance soil biodiversity	7 Reduce the EU global footprint on soils	8 Improve soil literacy in society

TWO SPECIFIC MISSION SOIL LIVING LAB TOPICS FOR 2026

- 1 Living labs to enhance soil health in Alpine and Atlantic biogeographical regions
- 2 Living labs to enhance soil health in managed forests and in natural/semi-natural lands

THE SOIL HEALTH LIVING LABS ARE...

“user-centered, place-based and transdisciplinary research and innovation ecosystems, which involve land managers, scientists and other relevant partners in systemic research and codesign, testing, monitoring, and evaluation of solutions, in real-life settings, to improve their effectiveness for soil health and accelerate adoption.”

CHALLENGES

Soil Health Living Labs in Alpine and Atlantic regions must cope with environmental variability, demanding weather conditions, and diverse farming systems that require integrative approaches.

The main challenges that these Living Labs face are:

- To choose versatile solutions to compare sites, or to scale up results, due to high environmental variability and spatial heterogeneity.
- To reduce the effect of climate-related constraints like seasonal snow cover and short growing seasons (Alpine areas), or intense rainfall (Atlantic areas) on regenerative actions and long-term monitoring.
- To balance agricultural production with soil health measures in small-scale, fragmented and multifunctional agricultural systems (Alpine), and in intensive grasslands, livestock systems and high-input arable lands (Atlantic).

WHO CAN BE INVOLVED?

THE QUADRUPLE HELIX – TYPES OF STAKEHOLDERS INVOLVED IN LIVING LABS

An essential characteristic of the Living Lab methodology is the **user-centric approach**, with the involvement of all relevant actors and end-users. While the specific actors will differ according to the Living Lab focus, objective, and context, all the actors can be classified according to the Quadruple Helix Model which is an extension of the typical Public Private Partnership.

The **Quadruple Helix Model** involves representatives from all members of society. These together form what we call Public Private People Partnership (PPPP) that enables real co-creation and impact.

Examples of stakeholders of Soil Health Living Lab in Alpine and Atlantic biogeographical regions:

- **Government & Public sector:** Regional environmental agencies, agricultural and rural development authorities, and water and river-basin agencies; local municipalities and mountain communities supporting land-use planning and resource management.
- **Agricultural sector:** farmers, livestock producers, and agricultural cooperatives who directly manage land and apply sustainable soil practices.
- **Industry and services:** Agri-food companies, seed and input suppliers, and firms providing soil advice, machinery, sensors, and soil-monitoring technologies. Tourism-related businesses (especially in mountain areas) are also important due to their significant influence on local economy.
- **Academia:** University and public research institutes. Field stations and regional applied-research centers also provide the monitoring capacity, and interdisciplinary support needed to design and evaluate soil-health interventions.
- **Citizens, civil society & users:** Farmers and farmer associations, local communities, land managers, and water-user groups who directly depend on soil resources. Environmental NGOs, outdoor recreation groups, consumer organizations, and educational or citizen-science initiatives can also play important roles in these regions.

WHAT CAN LIVING LABS DO?

WHICH ADDED VALUE CAN CO-CREATION BRING IN THESE SPECIFIC REGIONS?

Co-creation brings together **farmers, local communities, researchers, and policymakers** to develop solutions that truly fit local conditions, where steep slopes, high rainfall, shallow or stony soils, and strong seasonal variability can limit the effectiveness of standard practices. Co-creation brings a **scientific approach to local experience** to design measures that are both practical and understandable to local actors.

Co-creation also **encourages experimentation and innovation**, helping practices like adaptive grazing or cover crops evolve according to real needs. Collaborative monitoring increases awareness of region-specific challenges, such as erosion control, waterlogging, organic-matter depletion, or the need for low-input management. At the same time, it creates **opportunities for learning and adaptation** as conditions change. This approach supports long-term sustainability while being flexible and responsive.

WHICH TYPE OF ACTIVITIES CAN A SOIL HEALTH LL PERFORM IN THESE REGIONS?

In Alpine regions

Promote sustainable grazing with controlled rotation, maintain continuous vegetation on slopes, prevent erosion and landslides, restore representative habitats, and protect fragile mountain biodiversity.

In Atlantic regions

Restore peatlands and organic soils, improve water management in wet and low-lying areas, reduce nutrient losses, and mitigate flood risks.

Cross-cutting activities

Apply soil-health monitoring adapted to steep Alpine landscapes and wet Atlantic soils, test region-specific practices such as adaptive grazing, cover crops and water-management measures, and enhance collaboration among farmers, land managers, and communities to support climate-resilient land management.

CRITERIA OF LIVING LABS AND LIGHTHOUSES & HOW TO ENGAGE IN MISSION SOIL

LIVING LABS*

Aims

- **Innovation, co-creation**, formal learning
- Contribution to **societal challenges**
- **Improving soil health and related ecosystem services** (=> mission objectives)

Participants

Public-private people partnership:

- **Real soil managers** (farmers, advisors, foresters, city greens managers, allotment holders, etc.) to be at the centre of the innovation process.
- **Other stakeholders:** Associations and organisations with interest in soil health, local or regional government, scientists from a variety of fields outside of soil (natural sciences, social, and behavioural sciences), and the wider public

Activities

- **Co-creation, co-development & experimentation** of innovations improving soil health and related ecosystems
- **Research on impact of these innovative practices on ecosystems**
- **Networking** and **knowledge exchange**
- **Demonstration** (in particular lighthouses)

Context

- Multiple **disciplines** (-> transdisciplinary, inc. social sciences), **methods**, dimensions (technical, economic, social)
- **Place-based** approach and **real-life context** = real farms/forest/urban sites
- **Robust scientific setup** for **ecosystem assessment**
- **Openness**, communication, dissemination

**adapted from McPhee et al. (2021)*

LIGHTHOUSES

Criteria based on exemplary performances in terms of soil health and related ecosystems services.

HOW TO PARTICIPATE? ONE SPECIFIC MISSION SOIL TOPIC

*LIVING LABS TO ENHANCE SOIL HEALTH IN ALPINE AND ATLANTIC BIOGEOGRAPHICAL REGIONS
(HORIZON-MISS-2026-05-SOIL-01-TWO-STAGE)*

- Two-stage submission (applicants submit first a brief proposal outline; selected proposals are then invited to submit a full application)
- **Deadline: 14 April 2026 (first stage) and 15 September (second stage).**
- Supports the establishment of four to five living labs either in the Alpine or the Atlantic region - Proposals with **all living labs** focusing on soil health on forests or natural/semi-natural land types are excluded

Type of action: HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions:

- 100% funding for any actor
- Proposals must apply the multi-actor approach
- Support to third parties is allowed

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FOLLOW THE SOILL PROJECT!

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for updates

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SOILL HUB

A collaborative space
dedicated to soil health.

HELPDESK

A wide network of experts
ready to provide guidance and
answers on many topics.